

Creative Practice Research Outputs: Opportunities for Curtin University

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Glossary

Term	Meaning
creative practice research outputs (CPRO)	Creative practice research outputs (CPROs) are one type of non-traditional research output (NTRO). Not all NTROs are CPROs. CPROs refer specifically to creative practice research outputs such as novels, essays, short stories, digital artworks, and digital representations of physical artworks such as sculpture, films, theatre performances and scripts for movies and plays.
depositing	Depositing is where a copy or digital representation of the actual research output is saved to a repository, along with information about it. The information about a research output is known as metadata.
digital preservation	Depositing a copy of a CPRO to a repository is called digital preservation. Keeping a CPRO safely stored is especially important for creative practice researchers. In the past, copies of CPROs on websites of creative writing journals and galleries have disappeared online when these journals and galleries have closed.
DOI	Digital Object Identifier ¹ - a unique persistent identifier, with associated metadata also recorded about the research output
ERA	Excellence in Research for Australia – a national framework for research evaluation in Australian universities ²
evidence	Additional documentation that supports a creative practice research output, for example a program or recording of a play, or a chapter from a book.
FAIR	A set of guiding principles to make research Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable ³
metadata	Information used to describe an item, which adds meaning and can make the item more findable ⁴
NTRO	Non-traditional research outputs, a term used in the assessment of creative research outputs by ERA. These research outputs are works other than journal articles and monographs. Examples of NTROs include original, live, or recorded creative works; curated exhibitions; building designs and websites. ⁵ Not all NTROs are creative practice research outputs (commissioned research reports are also classified as NTROs). ⁶
OA	Open access
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID ⁷
registering	Registering or recording is where a record of a research output is saved to a repository. The record in the repository contains information about the research output, but does not contain a copy or digital representation of the research output.
repository	A repository is a digital archive that stores records of research outputs, and sometimes the research output also. The repository at Curtin University is called space, is publicly visible online and will appear in Google search results.

¹ <https://www.doi.org/>

² <https://www.arc.gov.au/excellence-research-australia>

³ <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

⁴ <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/describing-information/metadata>

⁵ p35 – 38, <https://www.arc.gov.au/file/3781/download?token=Wq9o-CbM>

⁶ p39, <https://www.arc.gov.au/file/3781/download?token=Wq9o-CbM>

⁷ <https://info.orcid.org/what-is-orcid/>

Executive Summary

In August 2021 the Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative (COKI) and Curtin University Library initiated a three-month collaborative research project. The goal of the project was to explore the role that open access research repositories play in supporting the visibility of creative practice research outputs (CPROs) by Curtin researchers. The visibility of creative practice research outputs to Curtin's research management systems; as well as the visibility and accessibility of research to communities beyond Curtin were key concerns of the project.

During the project a detailed audit of the process of depositing CPROs into Curtin systems was conducted. So, too, was a comparative analysis of the benefits and limitations of repository systems. This analysis considered the current repository recommended by the university to its researchers: Curtin's institutional repository *espace*; as well as three free services that Curtin is not formally affiliated with: Zenodo, Humanities Commons and Figshare. The repository assessment is included in this report in Appendix C, and current workflow analysis is presented in the internal report 'Repository and Workflow Assessment'.

In addition to the workflow audit and comparative analysis of repository services, interviews with six MCASI researchers explored how researchers currently share their CPROs; how they feel about sharing their CPROs; and researcher experiences of barriers to registering and depositing CPROs into Curtin systems.

The interviews reveal that many of Curtin's creative practice researchers are committed to ensuring that their work connects with and creates positive impacts for communities beyond the university. Curtin researchers are exploring the potential of digital technology to support activities related to 'impact and engagement' for CPROs. This includes sharing CPROs through personal websites, publisher and gallery websites, social media, and video sharing platforms.

However, the platforms and services that are being used by researchers to share CPROs with relevant communities are often not visible to Curtin systems. As a result, the university is not easily able to capture information relating to CPROs.

A disconnect exists between the impact and engagement ambitions and achievements of Curtin's creative practice researchers; and the capacity of the university to see and explore data relating to CPROs. An important factor in this disconnect is the practical difficulty that researchers face when they attempt to provide the university with information about CPROs via Curtin publication capture systems. The difficulty of making CPROs visible within Curtin systems may be a factor in the relatively low **number of artefacts (music, design, and non-textual creative works) recorded in *espace* between 2016 to 2021: just 35 items** (38 minus 3 mis-categorised research outputs).⁸

From a researcher perspective, **the process of adding CPROs in Elements is laborious and confusing.** Because Elements is the first step in depositing works to *espace*, the workflow itself has become a barrier to sharing CPROs and making them more visible. These difficulties, and the lack of functionality provided by Curtin systems, are prompting many researchers to look outside the university for research dissemination platforms.

Interviewees expressed a strong desire for Curtin's systems to be made more relevant to the work of creative practice researchers. Participants would like the flexibility to describe their CPROs within Curtin University systems using meaningful metadata, which captures the significance and impact of their work.

Making improvements to workflows and systems integrations has the potential to encourage more researchers to make their CPROs visible within Curtin University research output management systems. An opportunity exists to significantly improve workflows and capture information about more CPROs; as well as to ensure that creative practice researchers at Curtin feel that their work and its impacts are valued by the institution. This report summarises this opportunity, along with potential outcomes if these opportunities are accepted. The findings of this report are relevant to creative practice researchers, research facilitators, and the Research office at Curtin.

⁸ <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/browse?type=type&value=Artefact> then rank by issue date descending, retrieved on 02/12/2021

The key findings of this project are:

- Creative practice researchers at Curtin University need to manually intervene **four times** in the current workflow for CPROs.
- Elements has not been updated and is currently difficult and confusing to use.
- Because Elements has not been updated, it lacks key functionality that would ensure that it is compatible with other systems, including ORCID.
- Elements does not currently provide the opportunity to record meaningful metadata about the diverse range of creative practice research outputs.
- There is no official advice to creative practice researchers on where research statements and evidence for CPROs should be stored.
- In spite of these difficulties, some researchers have found effective strategies for making their creative practice research outputs visible to key communities.
- These strategies engage with platforms and systems that are external to Curtin University: personal websites, publisher and gallery websites, social media, and video sharing platforms.
- There is potential for free, external repositories such as Zenodo, Humanities Commons and Figshare to help support the visibility of CPROs for Curtin Researchers.

1 Introduction

At Curtin University, HASS (humanities, arts, and social sciences) researchers in the Faculty of Humanities are producing diverse creative practice research outputs, in addition to traditional journal articles and monographs. CPROs are one type of non-traditional research output (NTR). However, not all NTRs are CPROs. CPROs refer specifically to creative practice research outputs such as novels, essays, short stories, digital artworks, and digital representations of physical artworks such as sculpture, films, theatre performances and scripts for movies and plays. This project engages specifically with challenges that are encountered by Curtin's creative practice researchers when they attempt to capture their creative works.

In August 2021 the Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative (COKI) and Curtin University Library initiated a 3-month collaborative research project focussed on identifying opportunities to improve the visibility and capture of CPROs by Curtin researchers; and creating practical information and tools to support improved training for researchers about how to make CPROs FAIR. The project was prompted by a desire to understand the barriers that researchers currently face when attempting to make CPROs visible; as well as the potential for open access research repositories to help Curtin researchers to more effectively capture key information relating to their research activities. The visibility of creative practice research outputs by Humanities Faculty researchers to Curtin's research management systems; as well as the visibility and accessibility of research to communities beyond Curtin were key project concerns.

A detailed audit of the process of depositing CPROs into Curtin systems was conducted, and a comparative analysis of the benefits and limitations of repository systems. This analysis considered the current repository recommended by the university to its researchers, espace, as well as three free services that Curtin is not formally affiliated with: Zenodo, Humanities Commons and Figshare. The repository assessment is included in this report in Appendix C, and current workflow analysis is presented in the internal report 'Repository and Workflow Assessment'.

In addition to the workflow audit and comparative analysis of repository services, researchers located within the School of Media, Creative Arts and Social Inquiry (MCASI) were selected as a case study for this project, as they are active producers of creative practice research outputs. Interviews with six MCASI researchers explored how they currently share their CPROs, how they feel about sharing their CPROs, and any barriers to registering and depositing their CPROs in repositories (see Appendix A for the research project approach). The scope of this project was creative practice research outputs, regardless of their status in selection for submission to Excellence in Research for Australia (ERA).

The Chief Investigator of this project was Dr Lucy Montgomery, Professor of Knowledge Innovation at Curtin University. The co-investigators of this project were Professor Cameron Neylon and Niamh Quigley. This research project had approval from the Curtin University Human Research Ethics Office (HRE2021-0515) and was undertaken between July and December 2021.

This research report has the following format:

- Reasons, benefits, and challenges in making CPROs visible
- Systems and workflows for making CPROs visible
- A summary of key findings
- Insights, corresponding opportunities, and potential outcomes.

The appendices include:

- Appendix A – The research project approach
- Appendix B – A snapshot of CPROs in espace (almost 2% of the contents of espace, queried on 06/09/2021)
- Appendix C – The assessment of three free repositories

2 Making Creative Practice Research Outputs Visible – Reasons, Benefits and Challenges

The findings of this report are relevant to multiple groups within Curtin University. The needs and specific challenges of three groups, are explored in this section:

- Creative practice researchers
- Research facilitators
- The Research Office at Curtin.

2.1 Reasons for making creative practice research outputs visible

Needs of creative practice researchers

From the perspective of a researcher working at Curtin, sharing CPROs via digital systems is an important mechanism for making work visible to the university, as well as to communities beyond the university.

Researchers are required to record and deposit research outputs within university research capture systems (Elements and espace).⁹ Records of research outputs captured within Elements and espace can be used to inform career conversations. There is also potential for the information about CPROs that is captured by university systems to be used in other ways.

During interviews with researchers, a range of additional needs were identified:

- some researchers want their CPROs reflected in their academic profile
- some researchers want their CPROs reflected in their ORCID record so they can apply for funding
- some researchers want the ability to include more specific information or metadata with their CPROs when they submit their work to Elements and espace.

Needs of research facilitators

School, Faculty and University executive teams need access to data that can help them to understand the research outputs that the university is producing. This information is needed to support research planning; as well as to inform career conversations.

Needs of the Research Office at Curtin

The Research Office at Curtin (ROC) is responsible for wider processes of research reporting, including for the purpose of evaluation exercises such as the Excellence of Research for Australia (ERA). To support the reporting, evaluation and strategic planning needs of the university, ***research managers require information about research outputs that is as complete as possible.***

As an example, in order to support reporting for the ERA exercise, CPROs must be associated with accurate and comprehensive metadata, a research statement, and either a copy of the CPRO itself or a record of it.¹⁰

⁹ p3, Curtin University. (2021). Authorship, peer review and publication of research outputs policy. https://policies.curtin.edu.au/local/docs/policy/Authorship_Peer_Review_and_Publication_of_Research_Outputs_Procedures.pdf

¹⁰ ERA is a national framework for research evaluation in Australian universities, where research institutions submit their research outputs to the Australian government every few years. ERA calls creative practice research outputs non-traditional research outputs category which also includes designs and some reports. Not all creative practice research outputs produced by Curtin University are submitted for assessment to ERA.

2.2 Benefits to making creative practice research outputs visible

In addition to addressing the needs discussed above, sharing CPROs is associated with important benefits for researchers, their institutions, and the wider research community.

Direct benefits for researchers¹¹

Researchers who are supported to make their CPROs more visible will benefit directly:

- Research outputs will be more discoverable^{12 13}
- Could lead to new opportunities to collaborate with others¹⁴
- Potentially timesaving as there is research evidence for researchers to consult if needed in the future¹⁵ (e.g., the ability to provide a link to online CPROs if they are needed for future funding applications)¹⁶
- Meets funder requirements on open access¹⁷
- Saving research outputs in an institutional repository could add gravitas to the research by being associated with the research institution.¹⁸

Benefits for the institution¹⁹

Making CPROs more visible can bring further benefits – for other researchers, educators, future students, and anyone who consumes CPROs:

- Research methods can be re-used by others²⁰
- Research may have more diverse impacts due to being shared more widely^{21 22}
- NTROs evoke discussion and demonstrate creative research²³
- Research outputs are protected from being lost by preserving them²⁴
- Research outputs can be used to support teaching²⁵
- Opportunity to promote the school/faculty via the research outputs.²⁶

¹¹ This list of benefits has been extracted from p6, Quigley, N. (2021). Increasing the visibility of creative practice research outputs (NTROs): Literature review. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5336401>

¹² Burgess, R. (2019). [Getting to grips with NTROs \(visual arts data\): The role of repositories and libraries in their management](#). *Against the Grain*, 31(5).

¹³ Lambaria, K. (2020). [Considering creative activity in institutional repositories: An exploration of faculty perceptions](#). *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication*, 8(1), Article 1.

¹⁴ See Burgess, R. (2019) in footnote 12

¹⁵ Garrett, L., & Gramstadt, M.-T. (2012). [KAPTUR: Exploring the nature of visual arts research data and its effective management](#). EVA LONDON 2012 Electronic Workshops in Computing, 88–96.

¹⁶ Shelley, A. (2020). [It takes a village: Populating the institutional repository with performing arts content](#). *Music Reference Services Quarterly*, 23(3–4), 130–141.

¹⁷ Burgess, R. (2017). [From KAPTUR to VADS4R: Exploring research data management in the visual arts](#). In L. R. Johnson, *Curating Research Data* (Vol. 2, pp. 245–249). Association of College and Research Libraries.

¹⁸ Lambaria, K. (2020). [Considering creative activity in institutional repositories: An exploration of faculty perceptions](#). *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication*, 8(1), Article 1.

¹⁹ This list of benefits has been extracted from p6, Quigley, N. (2021). Increasing the visibility of creative practice research outputs (NTROs): Literature review. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5336401>

²⁰ See Burgess, R. (2019) in footnote 12

²¹ See Burgess, R. (2019) in footnote 12

²² Simons, N., & Richardson, J. (2013). *New content in digital repositories: The changing research landscape*. Chandos Publishing.

²³ See Burgess, R. (2019) in footnote 12

²⁴ See Burgess, R. (2017) in footnote 17

²⁵ See Garrett, L., & Gramstadt, M.-T. (2012) in footnote 15

²⁶ See Lambaria, K. (2020) in footnote 18

2.3 Challenges in making creative practice research outputs visible

Challenges for creative practice researchers

One of the drivers for this project was that creative practice researchers are not reporting their CPROs on an ongoing basis, and the reasons for this are explored in section 4, 'Key Findings'.

Challenges for research facilitators and ROC

As mentioned above, Elements and espace currently provide Curtin research managers and facilitators with very little information about the CPROs produced by Curtin researchers. For example, at Curtin University the 'artefact' research output category in Elements and espace is defined as music, design, and non-textual creative works such as fine arts, photographic images, sculpture and installation.²⁷ The difficulty of making CPROs visible within Curtin systems may be a factor in the relatively low number of artefacts (music, design, and non-textual creative works) recorded in espace between 2016 to 2021: just 35 items (38 minus 3 mis-categorised research outputs).^{28 29}

²⁷ p34, Elements Self-help Manual V1.2 September 2020 (internal document)

https://staffportal.curtin.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Elements_Manual_V1.2_September_2020.pdf

²⁸ <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/browse?type=type&value=Artefact> then rank by issue date descending, retrieved on 02/12/2021

²⁹ Metadata for humanities research outputs is recognised as a pain point in the management of research information, and OCLC (a global library cooperative) recommends institutional investment in data curation. One of the functions of research information management systems (RIMs) is the ability to showcase creative practice research outputs. This is relevant for attracting potential undergraduate and graduate students, as well as research collaborators (see Bryant, R., Fransen, J., de Castro, P., Helmstutler, B., & Scherer, D. (2021). Research Information Management in the United States: Part 1—Findings and Recommendations. OCLC Research. <https://oclc.us-rim-report>)

3 Systems and Workflows for Making Creative Practice Research Outputs Visible

All universities have different systems, workflows, and levels of administrative support for creative practice researchers. This section describes two approaches from Australian universities that are well-regarded for creative practice research: University of Sydney and RMIT. It also contrasts versions of Elements and DSpace in use by two Australian and New Zealand universities.

This section of the report contrasts the researcher workflow for journal articles with the workflow for CPROs. This highlights the important differences between the current capacity of Curtin systems to capture journal articles; their capacity to capture CPROs; and the level of additional work that creative practice researchers must do to make their work visible within Curtin systems. The contrast between the relative ease with which journal articles can be made visible to Curtin systems; and the difficult, complex, and time-consuming workflows that creative practice researchers must deal with provides important context for the findings and recommendations identified in section 4 of this report.

3.1 Workflows and systems at other universities

In the University of Sydney workflow, research support staff perform data entry into their research management system (Integrated Research Management Application or IRMA); then the Research Portfolio Data Acquisitions NTRO team verify the output and associated documentation, and coordinate with the researcher and School/Faculty/Department.³⁰

At RMIT, the NTRO guidelines³¹ include the recommendation to “host your ERA compliant NTRO in the RMIT Research Repository or any other stable and shareable location. Host non-ERA reportable NTROs and datasets in Figshare”. The RMIT repository is a library catalogue style Esporo research from ExLibris, where the research statement is included as an abstract. RMIT also offers an institutional version of Figshare at <https://rmit.figshare.com/>.

3.2 What versions of Elements and DSpace are other universities running?

Like Curtin University, many other universities use a combination of Elements as their research output management system, and DSpace as their institutional repository. It is notable that **the versions of Elements and DSpace in use at Curtin University are not as up to date as at other universities.**

	Curtin University	Griffith University	University of Auckland
Elements	5.14 (2019)	6.3 ³²	>5.19 planned 6.2
DSpace	5.5 (2017)	6.3	6.3

³⁰ University of Sydney. (2021). University guidelines for non-traditional research outputs (NTROs). <https://www.sydney.edu.au/dam/intranet/documents/research-support/reporting/ntros/ntro-guidelines-sydney.pdf>

³¹ <https://rmit.libguides.com/c.php?g=944007&p=6837734>

³² Upgraded from Elements v5 to v6.3 in 2021 (personal communication with Griffith University Library)

3.3 Current researcher workflows at Curtin University³³

The following workflows were documented with input from MCASI researchers, Library staff, and ROC staff.

3.3.1 Researcher workflow for journal articles

Many journal articles are indexed in Scopus or Web of Science, therefore these research outputs are often automatically found and harvested by Elements and ORCID (see Figure 1). Elements and ORCID import all of the metadata they need from Scopus and CrossRef. Generally, the process for researchers to have their journal articles added to Elements, espace and ORCID is much more straightforward than for CPROs.

Current researcher workflow – journal articles

Figure 1 – Researcher workflow for journal articles

3.3.2 Researcher workflow for creative practice research outputs

During interviews, creative practice researchers at Curtin University shared how they need to manually intervene **four times** in the current workflow (see Figure 2):

- go to Elements, add a new publication, and manually add metadata for the CPRO
- also in Elements, manually upload a copy of the creative practice research output that will be pushed into espace
- write and submit a research statement (and evidence if required) – ROC have advised there is currently nowhere to save or send them to, and research statements and evidence are not currently within scope to be stored in espace
- in ORCID, manually add metadata for the creative practice research output (the same metadata that was previously manually added to Elements)

³³ This section on researcher workflows has been extracted from the internal 'Repository and Workflow Assessment' report.

Current researcher workflow – creative practice research outputs

Figure 2 – Researcher workflow for creative practice research outputs

Note that **the fact that Curtin is currently operating a version of Elements that has not been updated for more than two years, and therefore lacks key functionality including ORCID read-write workflows, creates additional challenges for any workflow recommendations made by this report.** Because Elements has not been updated, there is no workflow option that can deliver a single step solution for CPROs by Curtin researchers.

Unless Elements is updated; or Curtin moves away from Elements altogether; researchers have no option but to manually add metadata to Elements and push the CPRO to espace via Elements. However, it is likely that CPROs in Zenodo, Figshare and Humanities Common CORE would be automatically found by ORCID, thus removing the need for researchers to manually add a record of their CPROs to ORCID. This would be an improvement to the current workflow, where creative practice researchers must manually enter their creative practice research outputs in ORCID. However, creative practice researchers would still need to manually intervene three times when adding a new CPRO – in Elements, uploading to a repository, and recording a research statement and evidence.

4 Key Findings

This research project set out to explore the barriers to making creative practice research outputs visible. This section summarises key findings from interviews with six researchers (deidentified as P1 – P6). Deidentified transcripts of all interviews are available as open research data.³⁴

4.1 Current dissemination practices for CPROs

The researchers interviewed are already sharing their creative practice research outputs external to Curtin University via personal websites,³⁵ publisher and gallery websites, social media, and video sharing platforms.

I have my website which is the archive of everything [...] My website does it better (P1)

I'm more interested in a much more public audience rather than academic (P4)

The peer-reviewers and peer review processes that Curtin's creative practitioners are engaging with are often operating in professional contexts, outside of academia. Similarly, many of the awards and forms of professional recognition that are most highly prized by creative practitioners are also outside of academia. Creative practice researchers rely on publisher and gallery websites to curate and share their work. Dissemination is not always a priority for some creative practitioners, who may feel that their work ends once a CPRO has been created.

4.2 Perceptions of Elements and espace

Some researchers reported that Elements is difficult to use, and compliance is not monitored. The lack of communication around which field of research would be submitted in ERA led to some researchers questioning the point of recording their CPROs.

... it's too much trouble to put them into the system (P5)

There's always all this talk of make sure everything's entered in, but never sort of chases us or says anything about it (P3)

There is low awareness of espace as a repository, and a lack of understanding of what espace is. This could be because all deposits to espace are via Elements.

No one can access espace can they? (P1)

I don't think anyone really pays any attention to espace ... (P2)

4.3 Barriers to registering creative practice research outputs

The systems and workflows in place internally at Curtin University to register CPROs are currently so laborious and confusing, that many researchers have chosen not to use them.

I think what I did the last time I tried, because it's also so time-consuming to put the stuff up, the last time I tried I actually just kind of went I don't know how to do this so I gave up. And thinking I'll come back to it when I've got a bit more time and then I never have it (P6)

The thought of having to write research statements is also blocking some researchers from adding their work to Elements, which means it takes longer to get into espace. At Curtin University there is no direction on where researchers are expected to store their research statements, and research statements are not displayed in espace.

But then again I probably wouldn't ask anyone cos I know I've got to go away and write the research statements which takes a lot of time. So therefore I've got to do the work before I can even ask for someone to help (P1)

³⁴ Quigley, N. (2021). HRE 2021-0515 Research Data: Interview Transcripts (Version 2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774508>

³⁵ Examples of personal websites of creative practice researchers can be found in section 3 of the 'Repository and Metadata Guide for Creative Practice Researchers' <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5860641>

4.4 Barriers to depositing creative practice research outputs

Some of the researchers would be happy to share a copy of their research output in Elements, but had not for previous works. There was a low awareness of the digital preservation function of institutional repositories in general.³⁶

Sharing is not as important for some researchers who don't mind if no-one reads their CPROs:

Then I get it done, or it's published so it's finished now, I can't do anything more about that, that's gone. And I don't put much at all into sharing it or publicising. I'm not necessarily proud or even happy about that, but that's the way, that's the way I do stuff (P5)

One interviewee was mindful of how the creative industry needs income to survive, and this was a barrier to them sharing copies of some of their work:

But really it's the creative industry, particularly the literary industry in Australia is very small and very fragile, and journals go bust and run out of money all the time. And they're good journals. (P2)

The impact of the current workflow is wasted time for researchers, a lack of meaningful metadata in Curtin systems, and poor visibility of research for research facilitators in MCASI and research administrators in ROC. This administrative burden is a barrier to creative practice researchers to add their CPROs to Curtin University systems.

4.5 Metadata important to researchers

Interviews included a card sort activity where the six interviewees were asked what metadata was important for them to see describing their research outputs. Researchers first filled in blank cards, and then selected from a number of best practice options to build their own metadata set. There was an excellent awareness of metadata among researchers, and they were all engaged with this activity.

The main finding from the card sort activity is that meaningful metadata is not being currently collected in Elements. For example, the Elements form to add an 'Artefact' groups together music, architectural designs, fine arts, photographic images, sculpture, and installation as one type of research with the same metadata fields for all.³⁷

This lack of meaningful metadata is important because some metadata about CPRO carries underlying information about the significance of a CPRO. For example, a play with a longer duration, multiple performances, awards, or great reviews indicates that it is likely a significant work (P6). Currently for plays, Elements does not capture the duration, multiple performances, awards, or reviews. There is no process to feed external recognition back into metadata, for example where an award or prize happens after a CPRO has been completed. Elements does not have metadata fields for Awards or Reviews, which would be useful for ERA and Engagement and Impact.

This meaningful metadata is missing in Elements, and therefore not flowing through to espace. Enabling the creator to add this metadata would contribute to richer metadata in espace about CPROs, and better information being available for ERA submission.

³⁶ Note that digital preservation is not provided as a feature of espace at Curtin University

³⁷ Quigley, N. (2021). Increasing the Visibility of Creative Practice Research Outputs: Metadata Findings from Card Sort Activity (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774660>

5 Insights and Opportunities

Interview participants provided many insights on what is preventing them from making more of their CPROs visible. This section summarises these insights as opportunities, along with the potential outcomes if the opportunities are adopted. These insights are presented in two categories:

- Systems and workflows
- Researcher behaviour

This section concludes with points of intervention for these opportunities, current strengths, and how CPROs can be made more FAIR (**F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable).³⁸

³⁸ <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

5.1 Systems and workflows – insights, opportunities, and potential outcomes

	Insight	Opportunity	Outcome
A1	The workflow for researchers who create CPROs is currently spread across Elements and espace. These systems have different business owners, so there has been no single person or team that has taken responsibility for this workflow relevant to creative practice researchers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nominate a role with responsibility for overseeing this workflow, with appropriate resources Consult with researchers when considering changing the workflow for CPROs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The nominated role will have agency to improve the workflow for researchers to make their CPROs visible to Curtin
A2	Elements is difficult to use, and compliance is not monitored	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acceptance that the current workflow is confusing and laborious for researchers is an opportunity to change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A better workflow with less manual intervention could lead to researchers having higher engagement with Curtin systems
A3	<p>Element types and metadata for CPROs do not adequately describe the types of CPROs produced at Curtin University.</p> <p>For example, the Elements form to add an ‘Artefact’ groups together music, architectural designs, fine arts, photographic images, sculpture, and installation as one type of research output with the same metadata fields for all.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update Elements forms in consultation with researchers who produce CPROs so that the types correspond to what researchers are actually creating, and capture rich metadata. Elements to espace crosswalks, and Trove harvest mapping may also need to be updated. See Appendix B in the internal ‘Repository and Workflow Assessment’ for detailed Elements issues. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More metadata will flow through to espace, thus making well-described CPROs more findable³⁹ outside of Curtin University e.g., in Google searches Upload and access statistics may be higher in espace, and usable in the promotions process⁴⁰
A4	<p>Metadata that is meaningful to researchers is not being captured in Elements or espace.</p> <p>For example, a play with a longer duration, multiple performances, awards, or great reviews indicates that it is likely a significant work.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enable researchers to record meaningful metadata in Elements/espace See section 5 in ‘Metadata Findings from Card Sort Activity’ for details of CPRO specific metadata requested by interviewees⁴¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Richer metadata about CPROs could contribute towards significance for ERA submissions

³⁹ p8, Nicholson, S. W., & Bennett, T. B. (2021). Do institutional repository deposit guidelines deter data discovery? Evidence Based Library and Information Practice, 16(3), 2–17. <https://doi.org/10.18438/ebliip29913>

⁴⁰ p136, Shelley, A. (2020). It takes a village: Populating the institutional repository with performing arts content. Music Reference Services Quarterly, 23(3–4), 130–141. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10588167.2020.1786308>

⁴¹ Quigley, N. (2021). Increasing the visibility of creative practice research outputs: Metadata findings from card sort activity. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774660>

	Insight	Opportunity	Outcome
A5	There is no process to feed external recognition back into metadata, for example where an award or prize happens after a CPRO has been completed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enable researchers to record Awards in Elements/espace 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Richer metadata about CPRO awards could contribute towards Engagement and Impact submissions
A6	<p>The version of Elements (v5.14) installed at Curtin University cannot send publication records to ORCID. Researchers can currently authenticate their ORCIDs in Elements, Elements gets new persistent identifiers from ORCID (e.g., DOIs), then Elements looks in its own data sources for those persistent identifiers.</p> <p>The current method of exporting from Elements to ORCID is via a manual export from Elements to a citation file, then a manual import from the citation file to ORCID.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Upgrade Elements > v5.20 to configure and implement Elements Write integration functionality. Elements will then support a true connection with ORCID. Researchers will be able to send their research output records from Elements to ORCID⁴² 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CPRO records will be sent from Elements to ORCID The metadata entered by researchers for their CPRO in Elements will be re-used in ORCID, thus saving researchers from double-entry of data.
A7	Current version of DSpace (v5.5) installed at Curtin University is not configured to automatically mint DOIs as a function within DSpace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Upgrade DSpace > v6.3 (version in use by other unis who also use DSpace and Elements e.g., Griffith University and University of Auckland). Note that this could require a contract with DataCite, and possible minting costs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The use of DOIs for creative practice research outputs will enable the re-use of metadata entered by the researcher in ORCID. This will also mean less data entry for researchers.
A8	ROC has not recommended a system or location to store research statements and evidence for creative practice research outputs, despite being required for ERA submissions. Some CPROs in espace already have research statements ⁴³	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide a place for researchers to save research statements at the completion of a CPRO (this could be open access or private) Consider a collaborative program/practicum placement with Master of Information Management students to audit CPROs already in espace⁴⁴ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research statements would be available for ERA, rather than needing to directly ask researchers for them

⁴² <https://www.symplectic.co.uk/getting-it-write-with-our-latest-orcid-integration/>

⁴³ <https://espace.curtin.edu.au/handle/20.500.11937/76182>

⁴⁴ Joseph, P., Gregg, M., & May, S. (2013). Digitisation of the WA Welcome Wall collection: A case study. *Archives and Manuscripts*, 41(3), 183–202. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01576895.2013.829752>; Shelley, A. (2020). It takes a village: Populating the institutional repository with performing arts content. *Music Reference Services Quarterly*, 23(3–4), 130–141. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10588167.2020.1786308>

Creative Practice Research Outputs: Opportunities for Curtin University

	Insight	Opportunity	Outcome
A9	Lack of transparency and communication from ROC about how CPROs are selected for ERA submission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear communication from ROC to researchers about how CPROs are selected for ERA submission • Ensure any Fields of Research (FoR) that will not be submitted to ERA are still valued and visible in Curtin systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A better understanding from researchers of the ERA submission processes • Researchers working in FoRs excluded from ERA submissions will be reassured that their research counts even if it is not counted in ERA.
A10	There is a lack of guidance in Elements forms and the Elements manual ⁴⁵ on which CPROs belong in which type, and a lack of real-world examples for CPROs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update espace and Elements support material to include more examples of CPROs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better guidance for researchers could lead to less confusion when adding CPROs to Curtin systems
A11	<p>No copyright information available in espace for some CPROs, or on a repository level.</p> <p>For example, ‘Koombana Bay plaques’ by David Whish-Wilson has no copyright information in espace for the photographs and text.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • See UNSWorks (UNSW Open Access institutional repository) for an example of copyright guidance on a repository level, including a copyright takedown request form⁴⁶ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clearer copyright information in espace • Requesting copyright information from researchers could increase their engagement with copyright (see B6)

⁴⁵ https://staffportal.curtin.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Elements_Manual_V1.2_September_2020.pdf

⁴⁶ <https://subjectguides.library.unsw.edu.au/copyright/unsworks>

5.2 Researcher behaviour – insights, opportunities, and potential outcomes

	Insight	Opportunity	Outcome
B1	Some researchers interviewed are already sharing their creative practice research outputs external to Curtin University (via personal websites, publisher and gallery websites, social media, and video sharing platforms)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> These researchers have no barriers in making their work open access outside of Curtin University. This provides an opportunity for more tailored interventions and education on open access, so that CPROs are also shared within academic systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researchers will have more guidance about the benefits of making CPROs visible within Curtin University systems as well as externally
B2	<p>Open access is not always an option for researchers who produce CPROs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> not a priority for some to share some cannot make their works open access as they are sold via a publisher a concern that small creative publications would be affected if a CPRO was free elsewhere 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The understanding that open access is not a priority for some researchers can be an opportunity to focus on making a record of a CPRO with rich metadata. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Visibility of more CPROs, even if the actual CPROs cannot be viewed.
B3	Researchers are confused over what types of research outputs should be added to Elements/espace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create an institutional repository policy for espace including what types and formats are accepted, and how they are digitally preserved⁴⁷ Update espace and Elements support material to include more examples of CPROs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researchers will have more guidance about sharing their CPROs
B4	Low awareness and understanding of what espace is for	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Target this gap in education about OA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More researchers will be aware that espace is publicly visible, and returned in Google search results
B5	<p>The digital preservation function of repositories is not well used or understood.</p> <p>Researchers have outsourced digital preservation across various online spaces outside of academia including personal websites, galleries, and video sharing platforms</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Education on why using a repository is more reliable than personal and third-party websites. This is especially important for CPROs, as some are inherently more vulnerable, for example smaller publications and project websites dependent on funding. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More CPROs visible as open access CPROs will showcase MCASI and Faculty of Humanities Better digital preservation leading to smoother preparation for ERA submissions

⁴⁷ <https://typeset.io/resources/institutional-repository-policy-checklist-infographic/>

Creative Practice Research Outputs: Opportunities for Curtin University

	Insight	Opportunity	Outcome
B6	Little knowledge of copyright and Creative Commons in interviews with researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Education for researchers on copyright and Creative Commons – so researchers can achieve a balance between protecting their work and showcasing it	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• More CPROs visible as open access• CPROs will showcase MCASI and Faculty of Humanities• Better digital preservation leading to smoother preparation for ERA submissions

5.3 Points of intervention

There are opportunities for the university to intervene in order to engage with the opportunities identified in this report:

1. Showcase creative practice awards

ROC runs the annual Curtin University Awards for Research Excellence, which includes the Creative Practice Award for researchers and ECRs.⁴⁸ There is an opportunity to showcase current and past years' winners (and/or finalists) online, by including a link to the open access version of a CPRO where possible.

2. Best practice examples

A CPRO researcher could be assisted to produce a best practice example in space, so that it can be shared as a real-world example. The 'Repository and Metadata Guide for Creative Practice Researchers',⁴⁹ an output of this project, could also be expanded with more examples.

5.4 Strengths

The interviewees were engaged with reviewing the workflow for CPROs, and had a high awareness of what metadata is important to them. Additional creative practice researchers volunteered to have their work included in the project deliverable 'Repository and Metadata Guide for Creative Practice Researchers'.⁵⁰ This guide is available online for anyone to use, and has been shared with research facilitators and Curtin Library.

Engagement with ORCID as a unique identifier for researchers was also evident. Most interviewees had registered for ORCID. Two of the reasons for registering for ORCID were to use for a previous journal article submission, and for funding applications where the funder required an up-to-date ORCID record.

This project is of interest and relevance to the research support community outside of Curtin University, with positive feedback for the both the open access literature review,⁵¹ and 'Repository and Metadata Guide for Creative Practice Researchers'.

⁴⁸ <https://news.curtin.edu.au/media-releases/curtin-announces-2021-research-and-engagement-award-winners/>

⁴⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5860641>

⁵⁰ Quigley, N., & Montgomery, L. (2022). Repository and Metadata Guide for Creative Practice Researchers. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5860641>

⁵¹ Quigley, N. (2021). Increasing the visibility of creative practice research outputs (NTROs): Literature review. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5336401>

5.5 Making creative practice research outputs more FAIR

FAIR is a set of guiding principles which aims to make research data and outputs **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable.⁵² While it may not be possible to make all CPROs open access (Accessible), many of the opportunities listed above would contribute to making CPROs at Curtin University more in line with the FAIR principles.

Principle	Meaning ⁵³	Opportunities
Findable	Ensuring that both people and computers can find your work because it has a unique identifier, and is well described	A1, A2, A3, A7, A10 B3, B4, B5
Accessible	Ensuring that a record of your work is stored safely in a reliable repository, and optionally the work itself is stored safely in a reliable repository and can be downloaded by anyone who finds it	A1, A2, A3, A7, A8 B1, B3, B4, B5
Interoperable	Having a standard way to describe your work, (possibly using terms used by your research community) AND being able to show connections between your works	A3, A4, A5, A6
Reusable	Including information on rights/licences associated with your work to indicate if it can be reused	A11 B6

⁵² <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

⁵³ <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>; Quigley, N. (2021). HRE 2021-0515 Research Data: Interview Guide. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774543>

6 Conclusion

The aim of this project was to enable Faculty of Humanities researchers to make their creative practice research outputs more visible, and document what information (metadata) is important to researchers when describing their CPROs. Interviews with MCASI researchers showed that they are already sharing their CPROs outside of Curtin University's systems.

However, the workflow for researchers to add CPROs is so laborious and confusing, that it has become a barrier to making CPROs visible internally in Elements and externally in espace. In contrast with researchers who produce journal articles, researchers who produce CPROs must manually enter metadata multiple times, in multiple systems. Researchers want the ability to describe their CPROs using meaningful metadata, so that they can capture the significance and impact of their work. Other free repositories exist, and these could be used to meet the needs of creative practice researchers, while improvements are made to the current Elements and espace workflow. These alternate repositories are explored in the 'Repository and Metadata Guide for Creative Practice Researchers', and suggestions for improvement are described in the internal 'Repository and Workflow Assessment'.

The key findings of this project are:

- **Creative practice researchers at Curtin University need to manually intervene four times in the current workflow for CPROs, making the process very inefficient.**
- **Elements has not been updated and is currently difficult and confusing to use.**
- **Because Elements has not been updated, it lacks key functionality that would ensure that it is compatible with other systems, including ORCID.**
- **Elements does not currently provide the opportunity to record meaningful metadata about the diverse range of creative practice research outputs.**
- **There is no official advice to creative practice researchers on where research statements and evidence for CPROs should be stored.**
- **In spite of these difficulties, some researchers have found effective strategies for making their creative practice research outputs visible to key communities.**
- **These strategies engage with platforms and systems that are external to Curtin University: personal websites, publisher and gallery websites, social media, and video sharing platforms.**
- **There is potential for free, external repositories such as Zenodo, Humanities Commons and Figshare to help support the visibility of CPROs for Curtin researchers.**

Increasing the visibility of CPROs by implementing some of the opportunities in this report has the potential to support more open and connected practices within research communities, showcase more of Curtin University's creative practice research, and be better prepared for ERA submissions.

The authors thank the six interview participants for their time, and the four additional researchers who agreed to the use of their creative practice research outputs as examples in the 'Repository and Metadata Guide for Creative Practice Researchers'. The assistance of Curtin Library staff and ROC in answering questions about workflows and systems is also appreciated.

Appendix A – Research Project Approach

Research questions

The research questions for this project were:

- RQ1: How are MCASI researchers currently disseminating their creative practice research outputs?
- RQ2: What are the perceptions of MCASI researchers of registration, dissemination, and deposit of their creative practice research outputs?
- RQ3: What are the barriers to registering creative practice research outputs in a repository?
- RQ4: What are the barriers to depositing a copy of a creative practice research output in a repository?
- RQ5: What metadata is important to describe creative practice research outputs?

Data collection

Purposive sampling was used to invite interview participants within MCASI who produce creative research outputs. Six creative practice researchers were interviewed by Niamh Quigley in November 2021, across a range of output types including creative writing, physical and digital art, film, and theatre.

The researcher interviewed the participants in November 2021, with approval from Curtin University's Human Research Ethics Committee (HRE2021-0515). Following transcription, the researcher analysed the data with Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis approach⁵⁴ using the qualitative data analysis software, MaxQDA (<https://www.maxqda.com/>). The total duration of the interviews was approximately 6 hours and 15 minutes, with an average interview length of 62 minutes. The deidentified interview transcripts, interview guide, and metadata findings from the card sorting activity are publicly available in the Zenodo repository (for document locations, see the table in the section 'Project deliverables').

User group requirements

The following user group requirements were set out in the project plan.

Researcher requirements:

- REQ-R1 Identify metadata required to represent research outputs of Curtin researchers
- REQ-R2 Identify potential repository for Curtin researchers to share their research outputs, that can support the metadata identified by REQ-R1
- REQ-R3 Create guidelines and training materials for Curtin University's Faculty of Humanities researchers to assist them in making their research outputs FAIR (and optionally OA)

Research management requirements:

- REQ-M1 Recommend workflow(s) so that Faculty of Humanities research managers have a view of research outputs produced
- REQ-M2 Recommend workflow(s) so that Faculty of Humanities research managers can generate a report for contribution to ERA submissions

⁵⁴ Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oq>

Project deliverables

Document Title	Audience	Use/Location	Reqs Met
Repository and Workflow Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROC • Library • Faculty of Humanities research facilitators 	ROC and the Library can use this internal report to inform changes to the workflow for creative practice researchers. These requirements were not fully met as a workflow has not been recommended.	REQ-M1 REQ-M2 REQ-R2
Repository and Metadata Guide for Creative Practice Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creative practice researchers • Library • ROC 	<p>The repository and metadata guide includes sections on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choosing a repository • Uploading to Zenodo, Figshare or Humanities Commons CORE • Metadata examples for Zenodo, Figshare, and Humanities Commons CORE • Comprehensive metadata examples <p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5860641</p>	REQ-R3
HRE 2021-0515 Research Data: Interview Guide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROC • Library • Other research institutions 	<p>Other research institutions can reuse this interview guide to engage with their creative practice research communities</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774542</p>	-
HRE 2021-0515 Research Data: Interview Transcripts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROC • Library • Other research institutions 	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774508	-
Increasing the Visibility of Creative Practice Research Outputs: Metadata Findings from Card Sort Activity ⁵⁵	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROC • Library • Other research institutions 	<p>ROC and the Library can use the metadata findings report to inform changes to the metadata collected for CPROs.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774659</p>	REQ-R1 REQ-R3
This report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROC • Library • Faculty of Humanities research facilitators 	<p>ROC and the Library can use this project report to inform changes to support for creative practice researchers.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5935316</p>	-

⁵⁵ Quigley, N. (2021). Increasing the Visibility of Creative Practice Research Outputs: Metadata Findings from Card Sort Activity (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5774660>

How project goals were met

Goal	How this goal was met
<p>Goal 1 – Research output description & storage</p>	<p>The metadata required to describe creative practice research outputs was identified by conducting a card sorting activity with six MCASI researchers. The findings are described in ‘Increasing the Visibility of Creative Practice Research Outputs: Metadata Findings from Card Sort Activity’.</p> <p>Three free repositories were assessed for suitability in storing creative practice research outputs. The results of this assessment are described in the internal ‘Repository and Workflow Assessment’.</p> <p>Six MCASI researchers were interviewed about barriers to registering and depositing their CPROs in repositories. The findings are presented in this report ‘Creative Practice Research Outputs: Opportunities for Curtin University’.</p>
<p>Goal 2 – Education on sharing research outputs</p>	<p>A guide for researchers was created on best practice metadata for CPROs, and advantages and disadvantages of 3 repositories. This guide, ‘Repository and Metadata Guide for Creative Practice Researchers’ has been shared with Curtin University Library to become part of their help resources for researchers. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5860641</p> <p>Findings of this research were shared directly with creative practice researchers at the Creative Imaginations Symposium at Curtin University on 29th November.</p>
<p>Goal 3 – Reporting on research outputs</p>	<p>The current workflow for creative practice researchers to add their CPROs to Curtin University research output management systems is documented in the internal ‘Repository and Workflow Assessment’ report, and is reproduced in this report in 3.3.</p> <p>The ‘Repository and Workflow Assessment’ report includes the following information for the workflows using current and alternate repositories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advantages • Disadvantages • System & guidance changes • Researcher procedure to add CPRO • Research visibility & assessment

Appendix B – Snapshot of CPROs in espace

Creative practice research outputs⁵⁶ account for almost 2% of the contents of espace (1251 of 64934 items).⁵⁷

Fig 3 – Snapshot of numbers of all research output types in espace (on 06/09/2021)

⁵⁶ The following espace research output types were included in the creative practice research output count: Artefact; Curated exhibition; Film, TV, Media; Non traditional textual works; Performance (Music, Theatre, Dance)

⁵⁷ espace counts on 06/09/2021

Figure 4 shows the breakdown in espace for the different types of creative practice research outputs.⁵⁸

Fig 4 – Snapshot of numbers of creative practice research outputs in espace (on 06/09/2021)

⁵⁸ espace counts on 06/09/2021

Appendix C – Repository Assessment

The use case example that forms the basis of this repository and workflow assessment is a creative practice researcher who wants to record and/or upload their creative practice research output to a repository with the goal of making those creative outputs FAIR. Secondary benefits that may arise from this deposit include a record being made in the researcher's ORCID profile, information flowing into Elements and then on to other university systems, and the material being available internally for other reporting (e.g., ERA).

Three free repositories were assessed, with all repositories listed in OpenDOAR:⁵⁹

- Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/>
 - Zenodo is hosted by CERN, an intergovernmental organization also known as the European Laboratory for Particle Physics. Zenodo is built on the open source Invenio repository platform application,⁶⁰ and is funded by the European Commission (OpenAIRE projects), CERN and the Arcadia Fund.⁶¹ Invenio is available for institutions to install as InvenioRDM, an open-source repository application.⁶²
- Figshare <https://figshare.com>
 - Figshare is owned by Digital Science, a company whose other products include Symplectic Elements and Dimensions.⁶³ The repository <https://figshare.com/> is free, and Figshare also offers a paid customisable institutional repository product which is more customisable.⁶⁴ For this repository assessment, the free Figshare has been evaluated.
- Humanities Commons CORE <https://hcommons.org/core/>
 - Humanities Commons is a non-profit network funded by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and Michigan State University. Their CORE repository was funded by the National Endowment for the Humanities' Office of Digital Humanities, and was developed by Columbia University's Center for Digital Research and Scholarship.⁶⁵

⁵⁹ <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/opendoar/>

⁶⁰ <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

⁶¹ <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

⁶² <https://inveniosoftware.org/products/rdm/#faq>

⁶³ <https://www.digital-science.com/>

⁶⁴ <https://knowledge.figshare.com/institutions>

⁶⁵ <https://hcommons.org/about-humanities-commons/>

How to read the repository assessment table

The following table presents the results of an assessment of repositories against the following criteria:

- Persistent Identifier for upload – what kind of Persistent Identifier is assigned to uploads to each repository
- Register without deposit – is it possible to register only, without uploading the creative practice research output
- ORCID in metadata – is a researcher’s ORCID stored with the creative practice research output (and not for instance separately in the uploader’s profile)
- Text – does the repository support research outputs in text format
- Image – does the repository support research outputs in image format
- Built-in image viewer – can images be displayed within the repository
- Video – does the repository support research outputs in video format
- Built-in video viewer – can videos be displayed within the repository
- Harvest via Elements – is it possible to harvest this repository from Elements (thus removing manual data entry by the researcher in Elements)
- Import to ORCID – is it possible to import a record for a research output from the repository into ORCID (thus removing the requirement for the researcher for manual data entry in ORCID)
- Long-term preservation policy – does the repository commit to long-term preservation of research outputs. Digital preservation policies are important because they show how repositories ensure proper storage and backup of research outputs over long periods of time. This is relevant for ERA submissions where reference periods for research outputs span six years.
- Copyright/CC options – can the researcher easily select copyright or Creative Commons when registering their research output
- Closed access options – is the repository flexible about whether the research output can be closed access i.e., stored in the repository but not publicly viewable
- Link to ARC grants – can the researcher add an Australian Research Council grant to the research output
- Cost – the cost of a repository can include software licensing costs, ongoing administration costs (hardware/cloud/staff time) and cost of upgrades (staff time/upgrade consultancy costs). The three repositories assessed have no costs to Curtin University, apart from supporting researchers in using a repository.
- Stats – all repositories include view and download statistics for their research outputs, so this has not been included in the table.

Repository assessment

	Persistent Identifier for upload	Register without deposit	ORCID in metadata	Text	Image	Built-in image viewer	Video	Built-in video viewer	Harvest via Elements	Import to ORCID	Long-term pres policy	Copyright /CC options	Closed access options	Link to ARC grants	Cost
Zenodo⁶⁶	DOI	NO ⁶⁷	YES	YES ⁶⁸	YES ⁶⁹	YES	YES ⁷⁰	NO	NO ⁷¹	YES (via DataCite)	PARTLY ⁷²	YES	YES ⁷³	YES	NO (free)
Figshare	DOI	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES (via DataCite)	NO ⁷⁴	PARTLY ⁷⁵	YES ⁷⁶	YES	NO (free)
Humanities Commons CORE	DOI	NO	NO (via profile)	YES ⁷⁷	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES (via MLA International Biblio)	NO ⁷⁸	YES	NO ⁷⁹	NO	NO (free)

⁶⁶ The DOI registry agency for Zenodo, Figshare and Humanities Commons Core is DataCite

⁶⁷ While Zenodo does not allow registering without deposit, it is possible to upload an alternative object as a proxy for the research output e.g., a research statement

⁶⁸ Zenodo – Publication -> Other

⁶⁹ Zenodo – Image -> Other

⁷⁰ Zenodo – Video/Audio

⁷¹ A paid Dimensions subscription includes **datasets** from Zenodo, Harvard Dataverse and Figshare. It is unknown if Dimensions includes other research output types from Zenodo e.g., images, videos, and text. A search for Zenodo DOIs other than datasets in Dimensions suggests that Dimensions does not index all Zenodo types.

⁷² Zenodo – 20 years at least (<https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>)

⁷³ Zenodo – access options = Open Access/Embargoed Access/Restricted Access/Closed Access

⁷⁴ Figshare 'reserves the right, at its sole discretion, to change, suspend, or discontinue any part of the Service at any time without notice to you.' (<https://figshare.com/terms>)

⁷⁵ Multiple licence options are presented at <https://help.figshare.com/article/what-is-the-most-appropriate-licence-for-my-data>, but only CC BY 4.0 and CC0 are available in the free version of Figshare at <https://figshare.com/>

⁷⁶ Figshare provides closed access via a defined or permanent embargo <https://help.figshare.com/article/how-to-upload-linked-files-embargoed-and-restricted-access-items-and-metadata-records-only>

⁷⁷ Humanities Commons – Item Types include blogpost, catalogue, editorial, fictional work, interview, magazine section, newspaper article, performance, poetry, report, review

⁷⁸ Humanities Commons – Michigan State University 'reserves the right to modify, suspend, or discontinue the network, with or without notice, at any time' in the Humanities Commons Terms of Service (<https://hcommons.org/terms/>). Items deposited in CORE fall under these terms (<https://hcommons.org/core/faq/>).

⁷⁹ Humanities Commons provides closed access via an embargo, with a maximum embargo of 2 years